

Boron Complexes of Bifunctional Tridentate Schiff Bases

H. B. SINGH and J. P. TANDON*

Department of Chemistry, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur-302004, (India)

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Schiff bases with molecular formula, $\text{HOC}_6\text{H}_4\text{CCH}_3$: NXOH [where $\text{X} = -\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2-$, $-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)-$ and $\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)-$] react with oxybis-(diacetoxyborane), $[(\text{AcO})_2\text{B}]_2\text{O}$ in 1:1 and 1:2 molar ratios leading to the synthesis of $(\text{SB})\text{B}-\text{O}-\text{B}(\text{OAc})_2$ and $[(\text{SB})_2\text{B}]_2\text{O}$ [where SB^- is the anion of the bifunctional tridentate Schiff base] types of the derivatives respectively. The diacetoxyboron Schiff base derivatives undergo exchange reactions with 1,2-dihydroxybenzene or 2-methylpentane-2,4-diol. On the basis of their elemental analyses, molecular weight determinations, conductance measurements and the infrared spectral studies, plausible structures have been indicated.

DIMROTH¹ was the first to report boron acetate to be tetraacetate on the basis of elemental analysis. It was, however, Hayter², who carried out molecular weight and X-ray measurements and confirmed the structure suggested earlier.

During the course of the present investigations, the reactions of oxybis-(diacetoxyborane) with a variety of Schiff bases derived by the condensation of *o*-hydroxyacetophenone with hydroxyalkylamines have been studied. The results have been discussed in the present paper.

Experimental

Materials :

All solvents and acetic anhydride were purified by standard methods and were freshly distilled before use.

Oxybis-(diacetoxyborane) was prepared following Lippincot³ and its purity was checked by analysis.

Preparation of the Schiff bases :

Schiff bases were synthesized by the equimolar reactions of *o*-hydroxyacetophenone with the corresponding amine in benzene medium⁴⁻⁶ under a fractionation column, followed by the azeotropic removal of water liberated in the reaction. After the condensation was complete, the excess of the solvent was removed and the products were purified by distilling them under reduced pressure. These are yellow in colour and have low melting points.

Preparation of boron Schiff base derivatives :

To oxybis-(diacetoxyborane) in dry toluene the requisite amount of the Schiff base was added and then refluxed under the fractionation column. The

acetic acid liberated during the reaction was collected azeotropically with toluene and estimated to ascertain the completion of the reaction. The excess of the solvent was distilled and the products were purified by crystallization from the same solvent and finally vacuum dried (~90% yield). All these are solids, soluble in chloroform.

Exchange reactions of diacetoxyboron Schiff base complexes with 1,2-dihydroxybenzene and 2-methylpentane-2,4-diol :

1,2-Dihydroxybenzene or 2-methylpentane-2,4-diol was added to diacetoxyboron Schiff base derivative in dry toluene. The removal of the excess of 1,2-dihydroxybenzene from the resulting compounds is quite difficult. It is for this reason that the calculated amount of 1,2-dihydroxybenzene, according to the stoichiometry of the reaction, was always taken, whereas, 2-methylpentane-2,4-diol was added in excess. The rest of the procedure is same as before. These are grey solids soluble in chloroform.

Analysis :

Boron and acetoxy contents were estimated by the methods already described in the literature^{2,7}.

Nitrogen was estimated by the Kjeldahl's method. The results of carbon and hydrogen analyses were supplied by the Department of Pure Chemistry, Calcutta University.

Molecular weights were determined in boiling chloroform by a semi-micro ebulliometer (Gallen Kamp) using thermistor sensing. Conductance measurements were made at $28 \pm 1^\circ$ in dimethylformamide with the help of a conductivity bridge type 235 (ANU VIDYUT, ROORKEE) with the cell having a cell constant of 0.78 cm^{-1} . Infrared spectra were recorded with a Unicam S.P. 1025

TABLE 1—COMPOUNDS OF OXYBIS-(DIACETOXYBORANE) WITH THE SCHIFF BASES AND DIOLS

Compound	Colour	Analysis%			Molecular weight Found (Calcd.)
		B Found (Calcd.)	N Found (Calcd.)	OAc Found (Calcd.)	
(C ₁₀ H ₁₁ NO ₂)B-O-B(OAc) ₂	Grey	6.46 (6.50)	4.16 (4.21)	34.82 (35.48)	326 (333)
(C ₁₀ H ₁₁ NO ₂)B-O-B(C ₁₀ H ₁₁ NO ₂)	Reddish brown	5.48 (5.52)	7.09 (7.14)	—	376 (392)
(C ₁₁ H ₁₂ NO ₂)B-O-B(OAc) ₂	Grey	6.19 (6.24)	3.97 (4.03)	33.76 (34.04)	335 (347)
(C ₁₁ H ₁₂ NO ₂)B-O-B(C ₁₁ H ₁₂ NO ₂)	Grey	5.14 (5.15)	6.59 (6.67)	—	412 (420)
(C ₁₂ H ₁₃ NO ₂)B-O-B(OAc) ₂	Reddish brown	5.94 (5.99)	3.82 (3.88)	31.96 (32.72)	352 (361)
(C ₁₂ H ₁₃ NO ₂)B-O-B(C ₁₂ H ₁₃ NO ₂)	Reddish brown	4.78 (4.83)	6.18 (6.25)	—	425 (448)
(C ₁₀ H ₁₁ NO ₂)B-O-B(OC ₆ H ₄ O)	Dark grey	6.68 (6.70)	4.27 (4.34)	—	307 (323)
(C ₁₁ H ₁₂ NO ₂)B-O-B(OC ₆ H ₄ O)	Grey	6.37 (6.42)	4.09 (4.16)	—	328 (337)
(C ₁₂ H ₁₃ NO ₂)B-O-B(OC ₆ H ₄ O)	Grey	6.14 (6.16)	3.93 (3.99)	—	336 (351)
(C ₁₀ H ₁₁ NO ₂)B-O-B(C ₆ H ₁₃ O ₂)	Grey	6.55 (6.54)	4.20 (4.23)	—	317 (331)
(C ₁₁ H ₁₂ NO ₂)B-O-B(C ₆ H ₁₃ O ₂)	Grey	6.25 (6.27)	4.02 (4.06)	—	337 (345)
(C ₁₂ H ₁₃ NO ₂)B-O-B(C ₆ H ₁₃ O ₂)	Grey	6.01 (6.03)	3.83 (3.90)	—	346 (359)

Spectrophotometer in the range, 4000-625 cm⁻¹ using KBr optics.

Results and Discussion

The 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 molar ratio reactions of oxybis-(diacetoxyborane) with *o*-hydroxyacetophenonehydroxyalkylimines may be depicted by the following equations :

(where SBH₂ represents the *o*-hydroxyacetophenonehydroxyalkylimine molecule).

The reactions are quite facile and the products so obtained are of varying colours and non-distillable solids. The 1 : 1 derivatives get hydrolyzed when kept in the open atmosphere liberating acetic acid whereas, the 1 : 2 derivatives are quite stable. As evident from the addition reactions with pyridine, an equimolar addition of base could be possible only in 1 : 1 derivatives, the central boron atoms (except the one of the two boron atoms in 1 : 1 derivatives) achieve a stable tetrahedral configuration. This is so, probably because of the coordination of boron from nitrogen of the ligand moiety taking place through a dative bond. The molecular weights determined ebullioscopically in boiling chloroform show these derivatives to be monomers. In view of this, the 1 : 1 (I) and 1 : 2 (II) derivatives

may be reasonably represented by the following tentative structures :

To show the labile nature of the acetoxy groups in 1 : 1 derivatives, exchange reactions were carried out with 1,2-dihydroxybenzene and 2-methylpentane-2, 4-diol. These reactions may be represented by the following general equation :

(where HO-OH represents the 1, 2-dihydroxybenzene or 2-methylpentane-2, 4-diol molecule).

The above exchange reactions are faster in the case of 1,2-dihydroxybenzene than those with 2-methylpentane-2,4-diol due to the presence of very reactive phenolic groups in the previous case. The resulting compounds are almost similar in properties to their parent acetoxyboron Schiff base derivatives. These are also non-electrolytes, monomeric in

nature and undergo equimolar addition reactions when mixed with pyridine and this merely indicates the presence of a planar boron atom therein.

Infrared spectra :

The infrared spectra of the Schiff bases and their corresponding boron derivatives have been recorded and the following important conclusions may be drawn :

- (i) The broad and weak band observed in the region $3300-3100\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the spectra of the ligands and ascribed to ν_{OH} , however, disappeared in the spectra of the boron derivatives. The disappearance of the above band obviously indicates the coordination of phenolic oxygen to the boron atom.
- (ii) As compared with the spectra of the Schiff bases, two additional bands at ~ 1718 and 1605 cm^{-1} are observed in the spectra of the 1 : 1 derivatives and these may be assigned to the stretching vibrations of free and associated $\text{C}=\text{O}$ of the acetoxy groups respectively. The spectra of 1 : 2 derivatives, however, contain no such bands and thereby showing the absence of any acetoxy group in these compounds.
- (iii) A very sharp and strong band at $\sim 1615\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the spectra of the ligands is due to $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$. This, however, shifts to the higher frequency side in the spectra of the corresponding boron derivatives probably due to an increase in the bond order of $\text{C}=\text{N}$ caused on coordination from nitrogen of the ligand moiety to the boron atom⁸.
- (iv) In the spectra of the pyridine adducts of a few 1 : 1 derivatives, the bands observed at 1580, 1482 and 1440 cm^{-1} are due to the heterocyclic pyridine ring stretching vibrations⁹. The band at 1603 cm^{-1} in addition to the

above bands in the spectra of the adducts of the exchanged derivatives may be assigned to $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$ of the pyridine ring. The shifting of this band as compared to its position in the pyridine (at $\sim 1599\text{ cm}^{-1}$) itself may be due to the coordination of nitrogen to boron.

Conductance measurements :

The molar conductance values ($10-17\text{ Ohm}^{-1}\text{ cm}^{-2}\text{ mole}^{-1}$) as determined in dimethyl formamide at $28 \pm 1^\circ$ are in accordance with the non-electrolytic behaviour of these compounds.

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